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FINANCING OF INNOVATIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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KEYWORDS

innovative activities, Ministry of Innovative Development, scientific-technical council, intellectual potential, technological potential, innovative reform, research, development strategies, fundamental research, applied research, foreign technology, joint grant projects, systematic monitoring

ABSTRACT

This article substantiates the innovations in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the environment for their effectiveness, the state support of innovations, the selection and financing of expert groups. The role of the state in the implementation of innovations is very important, as well as the use of innovative technologies in any field is a key factor in the economic development of the current period.

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Innovation, innovation activity, innovation process and so on concepts in our daily lives, in enterprise activities, and in the economy networks solid on various fronts is gaining ground. In carved in countries enterprises in increasing competitiveness, in the marketing position in strengthening and customer market innovations are important in the production of goods is one of the factors. Innovative activity - it is new in production or improved product type, new or improved implementation of the technological process or products have a better quality content that increases competitiveness manufacturer is the removal process. Innovative activity management mechanism or this the innovative developing of the subject purpose of migration or due to his direction, different combines a set of methods and tools. In the field of innovation management. The results of the decisions are ready market becomes a lever more effective development of the mechanism is the current state of our national enterprises is one of the most pressing issues. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated in November 29, 2017 "Innovative development ministry organization Republic of Uzbekistan the to grow about" PF- 5264 to the decree appropriate Innovative development Ministry organization given. This decree and President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2017 year 30 November "Activities of the Ministry of Innovation Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan organization to grow about " PQ-3416-son decision according to ministry Uzbekistan Republic innovative and scientific - technical development in the field society and all-round public life development and intellectual and technological capacity increase focused unique state policy make it happen increase state management body is calculated. Regulations on the Ministry of Innovation Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan priorities for the development of innovative development on the basis of, fields of science and 16 Scientific - Technical Councils have been established under the Ministry of Networks. Everybody one Scientific - technical council contains narrow in the circle industry experts and an expert consisting of scientist groups activity runs. Scientific - Technical Council Scientific - technical of the Ministry in each field of science to assist in the development and implementation of policies, state scientific -technical programs within executable scientific - technical projects evaluation, examination to do and from monitoring transfer with depending on work make it happen consists of leading scientists and thinkers in relevant fields of science public on a basis operating scientific team - technical team is calculated. Expert groups and appropriate fields of science and directions on provided scientific - technical projects, scientific - related to technical and innovative activities scientific - technical consisting of scientists and experts for the examination of documents groups is calculated. They are structure Scientific - technical boards by is formed. Also, ministry in his presence "Innovative development publishing house -matbaa house" by the state unitary enterprise "Science-fan and innovation development" and "XXI century technologies" named two scientific magazine edition is being done. The articles published in the journals are also scientific - technical council members to their conclusions according to to the publication recommended are given. "Science-subject and innovative development" in the journal articles scientific potential as a result, the journal is now recognized by the High Certification Commission given to the list of logs planned to enter.

Fundamental communication programs natural, technical and social humanitarian acquisition of new knowledge and legislation in the field of sciences, as well as practical research and developments scientific basis to create focused in, five until for a period of time manufacturer will be displayed. Practical research programs-country social – economic development priority directions current scientific - technical problems to solve focused important tasks effective solution to provider, resource Scientific - with options, deadlines and expected results research and technological development programs complex in, three until for a period of time manufacturer will be displayed. Fundamental and applied research scientific - technical programs government order based on, funded, scientific - technical directions, executive bodies, is a set of research projects identified by the leaders. Scientific project, the topic, purpose, tasks of fundamental and applied research and from research expected results marked scientific is work. Innovative implementation of the Ministry of Development within the framework of state scientific programs - 2019-2021 practical and current thematic research and innovation for the years periodicity of development choices, taking into account foreign experiences step by step - forming, set out to announce.

Selection assignments President Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan and decisions, President republic to the territories visit, report and in speeches marked tasks, as well as, Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Tasks of decisions and minutes of the meeting of the court, as well as the state, business management bodies and local authority bodies offer and from the recommendations come out, republic economy network and areas innovative development priority directions and functions on a basis formed separately worth noting. State scientific - technical programs within areas social economic implementation of development 2019- Practical scientific for 2021 - technical a competition of projects and innovative developments was also organized. The contests about more information of the ministry official from the website - (<http://mininnovation.uz>) get possible. Basic from choices again one this - President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 5, 2018 “Economy networks and areas innovations current to grow mechanisms Additional measures for improvement – measures” PQ-3698 decision execution provide for own costs itself cover on a basis financing priority innovation for, scientific - research, experience design and “startup” projects is the choice.

Presentation given projects choice requirements firm follow made, project materials reliability and authenticity, to the Department the way not set on initial technician from examination will be held. Else one important aspect - state scientific - technique programs within completed scientific - technical the results of the research after they are completed condition of full commercialization designation put down. Presentation to be applied projects organization scientific (scientific- technical) the subject of the project by the councils, its implementation and what is expected of it results economy network of the Republic of Uzbekistan and areas comprehensive discussion in terms of the need for development and recommended given about decision to accept required. Presentation given in projects information authenticity and reliability and choice winners by scientific - technical projects efficiency, commercialization degree, choice programs in positions

marked, expected scientific project managers, scientific project performer organization leaders and appropriate high organizations in charge employees are responsible. One choice in the early stages of the competition it is planned that the competition will not be held in case of project. In now and project of the subject relevance, his scientific potential, from the project the expected result importance and commercialization basis there is attention take, examination to the process will be given and project scientific leader with minister, appropriate fan Chairman of the Technical Council, Scientific Secretary, field of application, network representative will be negotiated with the participation of the results decision accept is done. Project positive conclusion has been in case funding recommendation are given.

This is to bring the research of scientists of our country to the international level urge with important. Scientific project provided of mandatory in terms the responsibilities of the scientific team are also set by the project manager. Then of his own scientific research results of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the legislation appropriate, of society unique property convert, them "Science network" (Web of Science Core Collection) or Scopus information base publication in the list, licensed domestic and foreign scientific publications need. Project practice application to grow in the process licensed indexed in the local "Science Network" or "Scopus" database and other required to be published in foreign scientific publications. Also different of the republic ensuring mutual integration with institutions in the regions, where the scientific-research institutions and higher training in their lands activity showing 40 up to was young scientists and researchers support - support for the purpose of "Academic mobility » in the direction qualification and experience increase for at least one young scientist or researcher is part of the project team must be entered marked. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2017 "Republic of Uzbekistan innovative development ministry organization to grow about" PF-5264, the Republic of Uzbekistan is a non-governmental development to the ministry country social-economic in development scientific-research works from the results use systemic monitoring bring go task submitted. The same at a time 1700 and more fundamental, scientific-practical research projects, innovative developments, young scientists fundamental and scientific-practical research projects are underway. It has also been in operation since 2018 joint foreign grant projects there is also. Monitoring from the transfer before project in progress to organizations questionnaires were provided. The questionnaire includes working programs of project executors, their project-related research - to the research work and project calendar plan compatibility, obtained by project important scientific results and their economics networks current to be made prospects, edition given monographs, textbooks, out manuals, scientific articles and patents provided to be made shown. Also, project complete in the process shortcomings, project bring causes and problems that prevent the project from going into place, the science in which the project is being implemented laboratory and material-technical base condition, additional modern scientific equipment-equipment, necessary consumable materials and component parts with information was requested on what to do to ensure. To conduct advanced research and

development in the monitoring process new type and modern high technological equipment - equipment with equipped with scientific laboratories organization to grow on suggestions, scientific and leading foreign scientific study to learn how to work on equipment from young scientists to send to centers for short-term scientific internships candidates give, project results with innovative at fairs participation to reach, structured agreements and their execution, work in progress organization by project complete three necessary conditions created like issues detailed marked. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2018 year 21 in September PF-5544 -Decree with 2019-2021 in years innovative development strategy Republic of Uzbekistan, make it happen increase on “The way map”, Targeted innovation development of the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030 indicators confirmed. Strategy head purpose of the country international the level of competitiveness in the field and the fact that it is innovatively developed determinant basic factor as man capital development consists of. One of the main tasks set in the strategy is the Republic of Uzbekistan 2030 until global innovative index rating on of the world 50 advanced is to achieve the ranks of the country. Therefore, scientific-research work more high steps lift both of the same Strategy basic from tasks one is calculated.

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